

Environmental Pollution

A proposal for producing calculated noise mapping defining the sound power levels of roads by street stratification --Manuscript Draft--

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Corresponding Author:	David Montes González SPAIN
First Author:	Juan Miguel Barrigón-Morillas, Dr.
Order of Authors:	Juan Miguel Barrigón-Morillas, Dr. David Montes-González, Dr. Valentín Gómez-Escobar, Dr. Guillermo Rey-Gozalo, Dr. Rosendo Vílchez-Gomez, Dr.
Abstract:	<p>The European Noise Directive proposes using strategic noise maps as tools to assess populations affected by environmental noise. It recommends using computational methods instead of in situ measurements when possible. A sound source's emission power is an important factor in the calculation of noise indicators. For traffic noise, this parameter is usually defined based on vehicle flow considering an emission spectrum that depends on the type of vehicle and its speed. This study analysed the possibility of using the categorisation method to propose an alternative method of defining a sound source's emission power to develop noise maps. This was accomplished using previously published values of the emission power per unit length. Another method is also proposed that estimates traffic flows. To verify their estimation capacity, the results of both methods were compared with the values obtained from in situ measurements. The results demonstrated similar uncertainties in both methods and were in the range of expected average uncertainties compared to the results obtained by calculating a noise map with the measured experimental values. In particular, for the differences between calculations and measurements, in absolute values, the mean uncertainties were approximately 2 dBA in estimating different long-term noise indicators. For the differences, the mean of the uncertainties obtained via the categorisation method did not present significant differences for the null value for all the analysed noise indicators.</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	Gianluca Memoli gianluca.memoli@npl.co.uk Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and population noise exposure
	Aleksandras Jagniatinskis akustika@vgtu.lt Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and population noise exposure
	Guillermo Quintero guillermo.quintero@upc.edu Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and population noise exposure
	Mario Mateus mario.mateus@adai.pt Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and population noise exposure
	Stylios Kephelopoulos stylios.kephelopoulos@jrc.it Researcher involved in environmental acoustics and population noise exposure
	Daniel A. Naish

1 **A Proposal for Producing Calculated Noise Mapping Defining the Sound Power**
2 **Levels of Roads by Street Stratification**

3 Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas,^a David Montes González,^{a,b,*} Valentín Gómez Escobar,^a
4 Guillermo Rey Gozalo,^a Rosendo Vílchez-Gómez^a

5 ^aINTERRA, Lambda, Departamento de Física Aplicada, Universidad de Extremadura,
6 Cáceres, Spain

7 ^bISISE, Departamento de Engenharia Civil, Universidade de Coimbra, Luis Reis dos
8 Santos 290, Coimbra, Portugal

9 *Corresponding author. Tel.: +34 927257234. Fax: +34 927257203. Email:
10 davidmg@unex.es

11 **ABSTRACT**

12 The European Noise Directive proposes using strategic noise maps as tools to assess
13 populations affected by environmental noise. It recommends using computational
14 methods instead of in situ measurements when possible. A sound source's emission
15 power is an important factor in the calculation of noise indicators. For traffic noise, this
16 parameter is usually defined based on vehicle flow considering an emission spectrum that
17 depends on the type of vehicle and its speed. This study analysed the possibility of using
18 the categorisation method to propose an alternative method of defining a sound source's
19 emission power to develop noise maps. This was accomplished using previously
20 published values of the emission power per unit length. Another method is also proposed
21 that estimates traffic flows. To verify their estimation capacity, the results of both
22 methods were compared with the values obtained from in situ measurements. The results
23 demonstrated similar uncertainties in both methods and were in the range of expected
24 average uncertainties compared to the results obtained by calculating a noise map with

25 the measured experimental values. In particular, for the differences between calculations
26 and measurements, in absolute values, the mean uncertainties were approximately 2 dBA
27 in estimating different long-term noise indicators. For the differences, the mean of the
28 uncertainties obtained via the categorisation method did not present significant
29 differences for the null value for all the analysed noise indicators.

30 Street stratification is a rapid and low-cost approach for road traffic noise mapping
31 without increasing uncertainties.

32 **Keywords:** environmental pollution; road traffic noise; categorisation method; noise
33 measurement; health.

34 1. INTRODUCTION

35 The World Health Organization (WHO, 2018) highlighted the adverse effects of
36 environmental noise on human health. Although different types of sound sources generate
37 noise pollution, road traffic is commonly the dominant source (EEA, 2014). Some studies
38 demonstrated different impacts of exposure to road traffic noise on human health such as
39 sleep disorders with awakening (Muzet, 2007), learning impairment (Minichilli et al.,
40 2018; Zacarías et al., 2013), hypertension ischaemic heart disease (Auger et al., 2018;
41 Begou et al., 2020; Dzhambov & Dimitrova, 2018), and annoyance (Miedema &
42 Oudshoorn, 2001, Sieber et al., 2018).

43 The European Noise Directive (END, 2002) introduced strategic noise mapping as a tool
44 for assessing populations affected by environmental noise. Both in situ measurements and
45 computational methods are listed in Annex I, although using calculation methods is
46 recommended (WG-AEN, 2007). Regarding the calculations, diverse standardised
47 models were used (COM, 2015; Harmonoise Project, 2005; NMPB-08, 2009;

48 NORD2000, 2002). Concerning measurements for noise maps, different strategies were
49 employed to date in research on road traffic noise (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2018; Gómez
50 Escobar & Pérez, 2018; Murphy & King, 2011; Quintero, et al., 2019; Rey Gozalo &
51 Barrigón Morillas, 2016; Shakya, et al., 2019). The grid method was widely used in the
52 scientific literature (Gómez Escobar et al., 2012; Martín et al., 2006; Oiamo et al., 2018).
53 However, some studies indicated that it does not provide an accurate estimation of sound
54 levels (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2011; Rey Gozalo et al., 2012). Based on the functionality
55 concept, Barrigón et al. (2002) proposed the categorisation method. This technique was
56 applied in cities with population sizes between 2,000 and more than 3,000,000
57 inhabitants. The number of sampling points per city was basically the same in this city
58 size range (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005; Rey Gozalo et al., 2015; Rey Gozalo et al.,
59 2013). The results showed a significant stratification of sound indicators among the
60 different categories and a high predictive capacity (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2018;
61 Barrigón Morillas et al., 2015; Carmona del Río, et al. 2011; Rey Gozalo et al., 2015).
62 The relationships between sound levels by street category and city size were also
63 ascertained (Barrigón Morillas et al. 2010).

64 The criterion regarding the microphone's location is fundamental during the
65 process of measuring urban noise (Mateus et al., 2015; Montes González et al., 2015).
66 Several studies investigated the influence of microphone position on the corrections to be
67 applied (Jagniatinskis & Fiks, 2014; Memoli et al., 2008; Montes González et al., 2020;
68 Montes González et al., 2018a; Montes González et al., 2018b). In general, given the
69 complexity of urban environments and the difficulty fulfilling the conditions established
70 in Annex II of ISO 1996-2 (2017), the experimental values of these corrections may be
71 very different from those indicated by this standard (Mateus et al., 2015; Montes
72 González et al. 2015). The presence of different façade elements are also factors that

73 should be carefully considered when comparing the measurements and calculations
74 (Naish et al., 2014; Tang, 2010; Wang et al., 2015). It is important to note that buildings
75 and urban environments are modelled in calculated noise maps by approximating their
76 characteristics and details, so this complexity in real environments tends to be simplified
77 (Arana et al., 2011; Lee et al., 2008; Montes González et al., 2020, Rey Gozalo et al.,
78 2019).

79 Another important issue in calculating noise maps is defining the sound power (Rey
80 Gozalo et al., 2020). For road traffic noise, this variable is currently defined using the
81 flow of vehicles (Harmonoise Project, 2005; NMPB-08, 2009). In relation to the emission
82 levels, some studies determined that there was a significant difference between the sound
83 powers within a single vehicle category (Brown & Tomerini, 2011; Coensel et al., 2016;
84 Watts, 2012). Brown and Tomerini (2011) found differences between 12 and 20 dBA in
85 90% of the vehicles in the same category on roads with speeds below 100 km/h. Watts
86 (2012) reported differences of more than 10 dB between vehicles in the same category
87 described using the Harmonoise model (2005). Coensel et al. (2016) concluded that the
88 distribution of vehicle sound power levels affects the estimated levels by up to 4 dB. Thus,
89 there are significant uncertainties in the results obtained using computational methods.
90 The validity of numerical model calculations must be confirmed by conducting in situ
91 measurements. Thus, considering all of the previously mentioned factors, WG-AEN
92 (2007) and others (Bies & Hansen, 2002; Law et al., 2011; Licitra & Memoli, 2008)
93 considered uncertainties of up to 5 dB.

94 Considering all of these uncertainties, some researchers assessed other alternatives
95 that could reduce the production while maintaining acceptable uncertainty values. Zhao
96 et al. proposed a new model of calculating noise maps based on the sound levels measured
97 through a prior street classification (Zhao et al., 2017). Ausejo et al. (2010) produced a

98 strategic noise map in Buenos Aires (Argentina) in which the daily traffic flow on any
99 categorised road with no data extrapolated from traffic data obtained from major roads.
100 Suárez and Barros (2014) implemented low-cost traffic noise maps in Santiago (Chile)
101 using a street classification according to the official classification.

102 In this study, the evaluation of the capacity to estimate the emission power of road
103 traffic lines is proposed using two approximate methods. In the first, a proposal is made
104 to reduce the costs associated with traditional methods. In the second proposal, the
105 objective is to analyse the possibility that the categorisation method can provide an
106 alternative method of defining the sound source's emission power in noise maps using
107 calculations. The results of both methods are compared with in situ measurements to
108 assess their estimation potential.

109 **2. METHODOLOGY**

110 The sound field's behaviour and the source power's definition in noise mapping
111 using calculation methods were produced by traffic flows and standardised (COM, 2015;
112 NMPB-08, 2009). To define the emission power of a sound source, such as road traffic,
113 the computational models use their own characteristics, such as vehicle flow according to
114 the typologies, average speed, type of flow, and type of road surface. However, collecting
115 the necessary data on each of a city's streets to ascertain the flows organised by vehicle
116 categories according to the periods covered in END (2002) is not a simple, rapid, or cost-
117 effective task.

118 To reduce production costs, this paper demonstrates the possibilities of using two
119 different methods to define the sound source's power.

120 The first technique, method T (traffic, MT), determines the power in a similar mode
121 to the standard way using traffic flows (WG-AEN, 2007). A simplified method of
122 estimating traffic flows in two steps is proposed to minimise the high costs involved in
123 obtaining noise maps, in which the traffic flow must be measured in each period for each
124 street in a city. In the first step, the necessary data from the sound source (flow, typology,
125 etc.) were recorded during two 15 min in situ measurements over different days and times
126 in streets randomly chosen to study urban noise using the categorisation method. In the
127 second step, the complete vehicle flows in every period (day, evening, and night) were
128 estimated using the data from 20 fixed stations to measure hour-by-hour traffic flows
129 provided by the city council of Cáceres (Spain) as a reference. That is, the city council's
130 fixed stations were used to establish the daily flow at our measurement points proportional
131 to the values obtained at said fixed points. Thus, the vehicle flows recorded in the short-
132 term measurements could be extrapolated to estimate the flows at each street in the city
133 during every time period using this method. Of note, to produce a noise map of an entire
134 city, it is naturally necessary to sample every single one of its streets (WG-AEN, 2007).

135 In the second technique, method C (categorisation, MC), an alternative is proposed
136 to define the sound source's emission power that was not previously studied with a very
137 low implementation cost. This is based on applying the categorisation method, which
138 allows the satisfactory stratification of urban noise (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2005), and
139 therefore it is expected that the emission power will be successfully stratified in this same
140 size range of cities. Five street categories are defined in this method:

- 141 • Type 1: Preferential streets for connection with other towns and interconnection of
142 those preferential streets
- 143 • Type 2: Streets that provide access to major distribution nodes in a town or are used
144 as an alternative to type 1 during traffic saturation

145 • Type 3: Streets that lead to regional roads, streets that provide access from street
146 types 1 and 2 to centres of interest in a town (hospitals, shopping malls, etc.), and
147 streets that clearly allow communication between street types 1 and 2

148 • Type 4: All of the other streets that clearly allow communication between the three
149 previously defined types and the principal streets in a town's different districts that
150 were not included in the previously defined categories

151 • Type 5: The rest of a town's streets except traffic-restricted streets

152 **Considering this objective**, results previously published by Rey Gozalo et al. (2014)
153 were used. In this previous study, the sound power level per unit length (L_{Aw}) was
154 calculated for each of the categories and each indicators L_d , L_e , L_n , and L_{den} included in
155 END (2002). As a result of the study, a significant stratification of the five categories was
156 obtained for the power corresponding to these indicators. These emission power values
157 are used in the current paper as input data in the calculation model to define the sound
158 source. That is, the second method enables the production of a noise map for all the city's
159 streets while considering only a set of five emission powers for each period during the
160 day. Consequently, the method's costs are focused on obtaining the emission powers via
161 measurements. Once obtained, no more sound levels or traffic flow data are taken. This
162 evaluates the categorisation method's capacity for producing noise maps by calculations.

163 To assess both methods, 32 new measurement points were selected on different
164 balconies in Cáceres. Figure 1 shows a broad sample of the buildings in which the
165 measurement points were located. The red circle points to the microphone's location. At
166 these points, week-long measurements were conducted following the ISO 1996-2:2017
167 standard's indications using type I sound level meters such as Brüel & Kjær 2260 and
168 Opera 01dB. Sound indicators L_d , L_e , L_n , and L_{den} used in the strategic noise maps were
169 evaluated based on these measurements. The 32 points covered the five categories

170 established in the categorisation method. This method verified that the noise maps
171 obtained enabled the estimation of the noise levels during each of the periods established
172 for all types of a city's streets from those with the highest traffic flows to neighbourhood
173 streets. Of note, as a result of this control point selection method, a wide variety of
174 situations were considered in the source's characteristics (number of lanes, road speed,
175 type of traffic, traffic volume, etc.), propagation path (U- and L-shaped streets, different
176 distances between the source and receiver, presence or absence of parking lines, etc.), and
177 measuring points (variety of the morphology of facades considered).

178

179 Figure 1. (a) to (p) Examples of the façade structure of the buildings where the
180 measurement points were located.

181 The results of noise indicators L_d , L_e , L_n , and L_{den} from this new long-term
182 measurement campaign were compared with values estimated by computational
183 techniques using the two previously described methods to establish each road's sound
184 power. For the calculations using these methods, a model of Cáceres with 3,020 buildings
185 and 960 roads was produced with CadnaA software v2018 using the NMPB-08 method
186 (2009) and following WG-AEN (2007). The following factors were considered in these
187 calculations: first-order reflection, default values of meteorological conditions (toolkit
188 17), building height (toolkit 15) of 4 m for the ground floor and 3 m for each additional
189 floor, and vehicle speed (toolkit 3), the maximum allowed for each street. Figure 2a
190 presents the model of Cáceres, and Figure 2b includes the levels calculated in one of the
191 areas studied through measurements.

192 In this calculation model, the receivers were located at the actual measurement
193 distances. Figure 1 shows significant examples of the usual architectural complexity of
194 the city's building façades. The presence of unevenness in the areas near the microphone
195 locations was associated with different elements and constructive solutions: windows,
196 outgoing balconies, incoming balconies, gaps in the walls, and façade limits near the
197 measurement points. Given the structural complexity of the façades and the prior studies
198 (Naish et al., 2014; Tang, 2010; Wang et al., 2015), the absence of sound reflections was
199 considered at most of the measurement points because there were protrusions, recesses,
200 or unevenness around the microphones higher than the ISO 1996-2:2017 standard's
201 values (see Figure 1). Only in those façades in which these elements or slopes were scarce,
202 small, or far from the measurement points was the presence of reflection on the façade
203 considered.

204 Figure 2. (a) Model of Cáceres. (b) Representation of the noise levels calculated around
205 one of the points studied.

206 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

207 To analyse the proposed methods' capacity to define the sound source power
208 introduced in the calculation models of the strategic maps of urban noise originated by
209 road traffic, the results obtained using the two models (MT and MC) were compared with
210 the measurements conducted at the 32 measurement points. Figure 3 shows the noise
211 indicators' values (L_d , L_e , L_n , and L_{den}) obtained at the evaluation points from the
212 measurements and the calculations produced using both methods. To make it easier to
213 visualise and maintain the same point order for all the indicators, the criterion ordered
214 them in increasing value for the L_d levels measured. Naturally, given the criterion used
215 for the representation, the measured values had a more uniform trend than the calculated
216 values. Figure 3 shows that the measured results were generally close to or between those
217 calculated and there was a similar trend in the results obtained through measurements and
218 those obtained using the two calculation methods.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

219 Figure 3. Sound indicators obtained at each measurement point using
220 measurements and both simulations. (a) L_d , (b) L_e , (c) L_n , and (d) L_{den} .

221 To analyse the goodness of the results obtained using both methods, a comparison
222 of the differences' means of the sound level indicators L_d , L_e , L_n , and L_{den} simulated with
223 the values obtained from the long-term measurements was made. First, to analyse if there
224 was a tendency in the calculated values, Table 1 shows the mean values of the difference
225 and standard deviation in which the sign of the differences was considered. The results
226 are presented for all the streets (global) and groups (main or neighbourhood streets).

227 Table 1. Average differences in the sound indicators between the values calculated by
228 both simulation methods and measurements

		$\Delta L_d \pm \sigma$ (dBA)	$\Delta L_e \pm \sigma$ (dBA)	$\Delta L_n \pm \sigma$ (dBA)	$\Delta L_{den} \pm \sigma$ (dBA)
MT	Global	0.3 ± 2.4	0.7 ± 2.1	1.3 ± 2.4	0.7 ± 2.2
	Main streets	0.4 ± 2.3	0.4 ± 2.4	1.4 ± 2.4	0.5 ± 2.2
	Neighbourhood streets	1.2 ± 2.4	1.2 ± 2.2	1.1 ± 2.5	1.1 ± 2.2
MC	Global	0.3 ± 2.2	0.2 ± 2.0	0.9 ± 2.6	0.3 ± 2.2
	Main streets	0.3 ± 2.5	0.0 ± 2.4	1.3 ± 2.9	0.4 ± 2.5
	Neighbourhood streets	1.0 ± 1.6	0.5 ± 1.6	0.5 ± 1.6	0.6 ± 1.7

229 The mean indicator and group values obtained were positive using both methods.
230 This may indicate that both methods of defining the source power predicted levels that
231 were far from the measurements in both directions but with slightly higher calculated
232 values than those measured (Bastián-Monarca et al., 2016). However, when both methods
233 were compared, method C (in which the source powers were obtained from the categories
234 proposed using the categorisation method) had mean results closer to zero. This may have
235 occurred because the sound source's emission power associated with traffic, when
236 defined by flow only, produced a variable that influenced the power in an important way:
237 for speed in the models, the road's limit value was usually used, while for the power
238 defined from the average powers per category, this effect disappeared. When the results
239 were analysed by grouping the streets into main and neighbourhood streets using both
240 methods and all the indicators, except for L_d , the main streets were those in which the
241 differences with respect to zero were the smallest and the group corresponding to the
242 neighbourhood streets was the farthest from this value. Of note, the null value was in the
243 standard deviation's variability range in all the cases.

244 For a more detailed analysis of the mean values and their variability range, Figure
245 4 shows the mean differences' values with their 95% confidence intervals. In general, in

246 both the global values and those corresponding to the main and neighbourhood street
 247 groups, the presented confidence intervals included the null value in its variability range.
 248 However, this did not occur for indicator L_n in some cases, in particular for the overall
 249 values and those of the main streets group using the T and C methods for the
 250 neighbourhood streets group.

(a)

(b)

(c)

251 Figure 4. Values of the sound indicators' mean differences calculated using both
 252 the simulation methods and measurements with their 95% confidence intervals for (a) all
 253 the streets, (b) main street group, and (c) neighbourhood street group.

254 The t-test was used to accept or reject the hypothesis that the averages differed from
 255 the null value. The results shown in Table 2 indicate that, for method T for the global

256 streets, the L_e and L_n indicators did indeed have mean values other than zero (p value <
 257 0.05). In contrast, for method C, there were no significant differences between the mean
 258 values found and the null value (p value > 0.05). This indicated that method C better
 259 defined the emission power. In particular, the indicators related to the population's rest
 260 schedule and therefore those most related to the nuisance L_e and L_n were better estimated
 261 from the power of the source obtained using the categorisation method (method C) than
 262 from the estimation of the traffic flows (method T).

263 **Table 2.** P values of the differences with respect to the null of the mean values of the
 264 differences. Comparisons include the measurements of the different sound indicators
 265 calculated using both methods.

		P value	P value	P value	P value
		ΔL_d	ΔL_e	ΔL_n	ΔL_{den}
MT	Global	0.422 ^{n.s.}	0.049 [*]	0.006 ^{**}	0.065 ^{n.s.}
	Main streets	0.498 ^{n.s.}	0.465 ^{n.s.}	0.030 [*]	0.388 ^{n.s.}
	Neighbourhood streets	0.076 ^{n.s.}	0.056 ^{n.s.}	0.113 ^{n.s.}	0.092 ^{n.s.}
MC	Global	0.482 ^{n.s.}	0.525 ^{n.s.}	0.055 ^{n.s.}	0.254 ^{n.s.}
	Main streets	0.591 ^{n.s.}	0.994 ^{n.s.}	0.077 ^{n.s.}	0.574 ^{n.s.}
	Neighbourhood streets	0.299 ^{n.s.}	0.252 ^{n.s.}	0.438 ^{n.s.}	0.239 ^{n.s.}

266 However, for noise maps, it is preferable to know the absolute differences between
 267 predictions and measurements. Thus, the rest of this section is dedicated to thoroughly
 268 analysing the goodness of the results obtained in absolute values. Table 3 shows a
 269 comparison of the means of the differences of the sound indicators L_d , L_e , L_n , and L_{den}
 270 simulated using both methods with the values obtained from the long-term measurements

271 (L_M) in which the absolute value was considered. The results are presented for all the
 272 streets (global) and groups (main or neighbourhood streets).

273 An analysis of the absolute values demonstrated that the mean values were
 274 approximately 2 dBA for both methods and all the indicators, while the deviations were
 275 close to 1.5 dBA. The L_e and L_{den} indicators had the smallest mean differences, while L_n
 276 had the largest. This may have been due to the sources' high variability at night (Brown
 277 & Tomerini, 2011; Watts, 2012). The highest standard deviation was recorded during this
 278 period. A comparison of the two methods of defining the power of the sound source from
 279 the results given in Table 3 shows that, systematically, the means of the absolute values
 280 of the differences were somewhat lower using method C than method T. When the
 281 average of the differences between the sound levels were compared using the t-test, no
 282 significant differences were found between the two methods for all the sound indicators
 283 and groups analysed.

284 Table 3. Average differences in the sound indicators between the values calculated using
 285 both simulation methods and measurement

		$\Delta L_d \pm \sigma$ (dBA)	$\Delta L_e \pm \sigma$ (dBA)	$\Delta L_n \pm \sigma$ (dBA)	$\Delta L_{den} \pm \sigma$ (dBA)
MT	Global	1.9 ± 1.6	1.7 ± 1.4	2.2 ± 1.6	1.8 ± 1.4
	Main streets	1.8 ± 1.4	1.6 ± 1.2	2.2 ± 1.7	1.7 ± 1.3
	Neighbourhood streets	1.9 ± 1.8	1.8 ± 1.7	2.2 ± 1.5	1.8 ± 1.6
MC	Global	1.8 ± 1.2	1.6 ± 1.2	2.1 ± 1.8	1.7 ± 1.3
	Main streets	2.1 ± 1.3	1.9 ± 1.2	2.5 ± 1.9	2.0 ± 1.5
	Neighbourhood streets	1.5 ± 1.0	1.2 ± 1.1	1.7 ± 1.5	1.4 ± 1.2

286 To fully understand the way the absolute differences between the calculated and
287 measured values were distributed in the set of control points used in this study and to
288 better understand the potential of the methods proposed for defining the emission power
289 of traffic lines, their distribution is presented in class intervals of 1 dBA. This made it
290 possible to analyse in more detail the global results found whose mean values are
291 provided in Table 3. Figure 5 shows the statistical distribution, and Figure 6 presents the
292 cumulative distribution using a class interval of 1 dBA. The errors in the intervals between
293 0–1 dBA and 1–2 dB were basically in the range of 20% to 45%. This implies that, in the
294 cumulative distribution (Figure 5), the 0–2 dBA interval was basically in the range of
295 60% to 75%. The 2–3 dBA interval had values generally ranging from 10% to 25%. This
296 means that the cumulative distribution between 0 and 3 dB had proportions that, for all
297 indicators and both calculation procedures, were higher than 70% and reached values
298 above 80% for indicator L_e in both methods and indicator L_d for method C. For the
299 remaining class intervals, Figure 5 shows that, in general, they were in a range of 0% to
300 15% using both methods and all the indicators, and the 3–4 dBA class interval had the
301 highest values, ranging between 10% and almost 20%. As a result (Figure 6), the
302 cumulative distribution led to values of approximately 90% using both methods and the
303 majority of the indicators. In any case, method C for indicator L_n reached a cumulative
304 value of approximately 80%, while for indicator L_e , this range already represented 100%
305 of the values. This better result of method C can also be observed in the cumulative range
306 of 0–5 dBA. Thus, method C presented a better estimate of almost all the noise indicators
307 so that the differences between the calculated and measured values did not differ by more
308 than 5 dB in 100% of the cases, except for the night indicator, in which both methods
309 reached more than 90%.

310

311 Figure 5. Statistical distribution of the absolute values of the differences between the
 312 values calculated using the two methods and the measurement results in class intervals
 313 of 1 dB.

314

315 Figure 6. Cumulative distribution of the absolute values of the differences between the
 316 values calculated using both methods and the measurement results with a class interval
 317 of 1 dB.

318 Considering the different sources of uncertainty analysed in the literature, the
319 statistical and cumulative distribution of the differences between the results of the
320 calculation models and measurements shown in Figures 4 and 5 were within the expected
321 values. These values were similar to those in other studies that found differences of up to
322 5 dB between measured and calculated sound levels (Bies & Hansen, 2002; Licitra &
323 Memoli, 2008). A series of factors inherent in noise mapping and measurement can
324 contribute to this range of uncertainty. WG-AEN (2007), analysing the uncertainty of
325 evaluation data, indicated differences in environmental noise measurements within 5 dBA
326 at the same site on different days. WG-AEN (2007) also indicated an accuracy of 4 dB
327 when official traffic flow data were used for typical road types. Arana et al. (2011)
328 suggested that uncertainties associated with terrain models can lead to errors up to 3 dB.
329 Other factors, such as the presence of parking lanes in an urban environment not
330 considered in noise mapping, may cause uncertainties even greater than 4 dB (Montes
331 González et al., 2020). Similarly, other researchers reported uncertainties associated with
332 the presence of building elements on façades not considered in models when evaluating
333 the sound level measured by a microphone (Naish et al., 2014; Tang, 2010; Wang et al.,
334 2015). Coensel et al. (2016) found uncertainties affecting the power of the sound source
335 of up to 4 dB concerning model variables, such as driving style, vehicle speeds, or traffic
336 flow. Naturally, if a combined uncertainty associated with all these calculation models'
337 uncertainties is considered in the way that, for example, the ISO 1996-2:2017 standard is
338 used to calculate the measurement uncertainty, the value obtained would be higher than
339 the maximum independent values presented. This suggests that calculation uncertainties
340 have the same order as measurement uncertainties, that is, with values exceeding 5 dBA.

341 Furthermore, the slightly worse behaviour of the two methods at night was neither
342 surprising nor a problem in the quality of the results. Previous studies also indicated a

343 greater dispersion of results in this time range (Licitra & Memoli, 2008). Of note, it is
344 difficult to maintain the same degree of precision in night-time methods as in daytime
345 methods, mainly because of the significant decrease in traffic flow during the night. If it
346 is added to low traffic flows, the variations in the emission power of the different types
347 of vehicles can result in very important variations in sound levels. As previously
348 discussed in the introduction, Brown and Tomerini (2011) found differences between 12
349 and 20 dBA in 90% of the vehicles in the same category on roads with speeds below 100
350 km/h, and Watts (2012) reported differences of more than 10 dB between vehicles in the
351 same category that were described in the Harmonoise model (2005).

352 Therefore, taking into account the results and the bibliographical discussion, the
353 proposed methods present uncertainties in the range of those expected. Moreover, they
354 represent a good alternative for assessing noise maps, especially in cases where there is a
355 lack of economic, technical, or human means of carefully applying WG-AEN's
356 recommendations (2007).

357 Although both methods provide acceptable and comparable results, it is important
358 to analyse their differences, the novelty they represent in methodological terms, and their
359 advantages in terms of resource requirements. With respect to the results, method C
360 behaved somewhat better than method T. Regarding novelty, method T has the same
361 foundations as those currently applied, while method C represents a basic novelty by
362 defining the power of the sound source from the strata proposed by the categorisation
363 method based on the usefulness of the streets as a communication system. Finally, with
364 respect to resources, in method T, it is still necessary to sample all the streets of a city to
365 produce a noise map. However, in method C, once a relatively small set of streets has
366 been sampled, it is possible to define an emission power for all the streets of the city.

367 Furthermore, in the range of cities studied using the categorisation method, the number
368 of streets sampled is independent of a city's size.

369 Owing to these reasons, the results showed that method C, based on the estimation
370 of noise indicators from the sound power obtained using the categorisation method, can
371 be considered an interesting alternative for defining the sound power of traffic lines in
372 noise maps. Of note, this proposal, with similar uncertainties to those of methods based
373 on traffic flows, implies a significant reduction in resources necessary for noise mapping,
374 which are greater in larger cities. In addition, as this method is based on emission power
375 by street categories, it allows predictions of noise levels in cases in which the authorities
376 modify the functionality of streets, establish new traffic regulations, or propose new urban
377 development.

378 4. CONCLUSIONS

379 Two methods were proposed and studied to define the power of the noise source
380 associated with urban traffic in noise mapping. The first method, based on flow, reduced
381 costs by proposing a system for estimating traffic flow. The second method, based on the
382 categorisation method, was used to define the source's emission power from a limited
383 sample of a city's streets.

384 The results demonstrated similar uncertainties for both methods. Considering the
385 consulted literature, the values were in the range of the expected uncertainties when
386 comparing the results obtained by calculating a noise map with the measured
387 experimental values. In particular:

- 388 - In the differences, in absolute values, between the results of the measurements
389 and those calculated:

- 390 ○ Both methods had average uncertainties of approximately 2 dBA in
391 estimating the different sound indicators.
- 392 ○ No significant statistical differences were found between the results
393 obtained using both methods.
- 394 - In the differences, considering the sign, between the results of the measurements
395 and those calculated:
- 396 ○ With both methods, the calculated values obtained were somewhat higher
397 than those measured, and those obtained using method T were higher.
- 398 ○ For indicators L_e and L_n , method T demonstrated significant differences
399 from the null value, while method C showed no significant differences
400 from the null value in any of the indicators.

401 Therefore, the proposals studied can represent an alternative for the assessment of noise
402 maps. Above all, their application can be of considerable interest when:

- 403 - A rapid and low-cost approach for assessing a noise map is preferable without
404 increasing the results' uncertainty and to understand a city's noise pollution.
- 405 - Producing noise maps in towns that are not required to do so, but the authorities
406 are interested in understanding the noise pollution with uncertainties similar to
407 those of other traditional methods.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Author Statements:

Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas: Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal analysis; Funding acquisition; Investigation; Methodology; Project administration; Resources; Supervision; Validation; Visualization; Roles/Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing. **David Montes González:** Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Funding acquisition; Investigation; Methodology; Supervision; Validation; Visualization; Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing. **Valentín Gómez Escobar:** Data curation; Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; Software; Validation; Writing - review & editing. **Guillermo Rey Gozalo:** Conceptualization; Formal analysis; Funding acquisition; Investigation; Methodology; Validation; Visualization; Writing - review & editing. **Rosendo Vilchez Gómez:** Formal analysis; Investigation; Methodology; Validation; Visualization; Writing - review & editing.